

Aqueous hydrogen peroxide and 2,4,4,6-tetrabromo-2,5-cyclohexadienone catalyst : An efficient mild ecofriendly cleaving reagent of thioacetals and thioketals

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Abstract : A clean mild efficient dethioacetalization protocol is revealed utilizing a catalytic combination of 2,4,4,6-tetrabromo-2,5-cyclohexadienone (TBCHD) (20 mol%) with 30% hydrogen peroxide as a terminal oxidizer in aqueous acetonitrile at room temperature. High yields of carbonyl compounds without overoxidation for oxidation-prone aromatic and furyl aldehydes, simple work-up, use of cost-compatible readily accessible reagents, tolerance of a wide range of common functional and protecting groups including phenolic hydroxy, methylenedioxy, acetoxy, aromatic amino, carbon-carbon double bond, allyl, benzyl, TBDPS ethers, NHBoc, NHBz are the key attractive features of the method.

Keywords : Thioacetals, thioketals, deprotection, 30% H₂O₂, TBCHD.

Introduction

1,3-Dithianes and 1,3-dithiolanes are versatile robust carbonyl protecting groups that are particularly useful for their easy accessibility and stability under acidic as well as basic conditions. Apart from their worth as protecting groups, 2-metallo-1,3-dithianes generated from aldehydes have proven synthetic utility as acyl anion synthons which are often utilized for carbon-carbon bond formation reactions¹⁻³. However, release of carbonyls from these derivatives is not always facile and often complicated with side reactions. Notwithstanding the fact that a host of cleavage procedures are currently available^{4,5}, a good many of these are based on stoichiometric or excess use of toxic heavy metal salts of Hg^{II}, Bi^{III}, Zn^{II}, V^V, Ag^I, Sb^V or SeO₂ or volatile CH₃I with waste disposal problems and other adverse environmental implications. The ubiquity of the carbonyl group with its synthetic flexibility as also recent paradigm shift towards development of greener procedures evoked considerable contemporary interest for newer dethioacetalization protocols under mild clean conditions⁶⁻⁹. An attractive approach towards this end is often based upon utilization of sources of soft electrophilic halogenium ions for their thiophilicity that result in generation of hydrolytically labile sulfonium ion

intermediates paving the way to cleavage to parent carbonyl compounds. Some of the recent cleavage protocols based upon NBS¹⁰, HBr-H₂O₂¹¹, NCS^{12,13}, bis-(trifluoroacetoxy)iodobenzene (BTI)¹⁴, Dess-Martin periodinane (DMP)¹⁵, *o*-iodoxybenzoic acid (IBX)¹⁶⁻¹⁹, I₂-DMSO²⁰, I₂-AgNO₂/AgClO₄²¹ rely upon this concept of "two-stage" cleavage process. However, most of these methods are stoichiometric methods often involving expensive reagents. In continuation of our interest towards developing environmentally benign catalytic methods using aqueous hydrogen peroxide or its solid peroxygen equivalents²²⁻²⁵, we felt that 2,4,4,6-tetrabromo-2,5-cyclohexadienone (TBCHD)²⁶ would be a promising candidate for bromonium ion equivalent. This *para*-selective brominating agent is prone towards nucleophile-driven aromatization with consequent release of bromonium ion by way of highly selective nucleophilic attack at C-4²⁷. It was envisaged that soft nucleophilic sulfur of 1,3-dithianes would facilitate departure of bromonium ion triggering the cleavage process and the bromide ion subsequently released could be oxidized back to bromonium ion in the presence of environmentally friendly terminal oxidizer 30% aqueous hydrogen peroxide which releases water as the only byproduct in the oxidation process (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

Towards implementation of this approach, we considered 3,4-methylenedioxybenzaldehyde (piperonal) as a representative of oxidation-prone aromatic aldehydes and chose its 1,3-dithiane **1** as a model substrate for cleavage. Neither 30% H₂O₂ nor TBCHD alone could effectively cleave **1** even after prolonged exposure (10 h). Initial exploratory experiments were carried out in water, with and without the anionic surfactant sodium dodecylsulfate (SDS). Attempt to cleave **1** with TBCHD (20 mol%) and 30% aqueous H₂O₂ (0.5 mL, ~4 mmol) in water (3 mL) also proved unsatisfactory. This failure prompted us to evaluate the micellar solubilization route to circumvent the incompatibility of **1** and the TBCHD in aqueous medium. However, cleavage rate of **1** did not improve satisfactorily either even when varying catalytic amounts of TBCHD in combination with 30% H₂O₂ under micellar conditions (SDS, 0.4 mmol, 5 mL water/mmol of substrate) were used. Use of acetonitrile as the co-solvent (CH₃CN-H₂O 9 : 1) dramatically accelerated the dethioacetalization process with vast improvement in yield of piperonal. The most satisfying result was obtained with a combination of 0.2 mL of 30% H₂O₂ per mmol of substrate with TBCHD (20 mol%) affording excellent yield of piperonal (98%) in 15 min (Table 1).

To demonstrate the generality and scope of the procedure a wide range of thioacetals and ketals, cyclic and noncyclic²⁸, were subjected to cleavage under the optimized conditions and the results are summarized in Table 2. A notable feature of the deprotection process is that 1,3-dithianes of aromatic aldehydes bearing electron-releasing groups such as amino, hydroxy, methoxy were deprotected with ease compared to their counterparts having electron-withdrawing nitro groups (entries 5-7) thereby

Table 1. Optimization of reaction conditions for deprotection of 2-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-1,3-dithiane (**1**)^a with 30% H₂O₂ and TBCHD

Entry	30% H ₂ O ₂ (mL) ^b	TBCHD (mol %)	Solvent [mL], surfactant (mmol)	Reaction time	Yield of piperonal (%)
1	-	20	H ₂ O [5]	10 h	20
2	0.2	-	H ₂ O [5]	10 h	No reaction
3	0.5	20	H ₂ O [3]	10 h	35
4	0.2	20	H ₂ O [5], SDS (0.4)	6 h	40
5	0.5	10	H ₂ O [5], SDS (0.4)	8 h	30
6	0.5	20	H ₂ O [5], SDS (0.4)	8 h	50
7	0.2	10	CH ₃ CN-H ₂ O (90 : 10) [2]	1 h	80
8	0.2	10	MeOH-H ₂ O (90 : 10) [2]	2 h	55
9	0.1	20	CH ₃ CN-H ₂ O (90 : 10) [2]	2 h	65
10	0.2	20	CH ₃ CN-H ₂ O (90 : 10) [2]	15 min	98

^aThe experiments were conducted in 1 millimolar scale at room temperature.

^bAmounts of 30% H₂O₂, TBCHD and solvent used per mmol of **1**.

Table 2. Cleavage of thioacetals and thioketals to the corresponding carbonyl compounds with 30% H₂O₂ and TBCHD catalyst

Entry	Substrate	Reaction time ^a (min/h)	Yield of the carbonyl compound ^b (%)
1		15 min	98
2		30 min	92 ^c
3		40 min	95

Table-2 (contd.)

Table-2 (contd.)

4		1.5 h	97
5		4.5 h	90
6		4.5 h	98
7		2.5 h	95
8		1.5 h	85
9		1 h	98
10		45 min	90 ^c
11		1 h	95
12		30 min	96
13		45 min	100
14		2.5 h	96
15		30 min	96
16		1.5 h	16a (80)
17		3 h	85

18		45 min	90
19		45 min	98 ^c
20		15 min	94 ^c
21		1.5 h	95 ^c
22		1 h	98
23		1 h	94
24		7h	72
25		1.5 h	90 ^c
26		5 h	60
27		45 min	92

^aReaction conditions : 30% H₂O₂ (0.2 mL, ~2 mmol), TBCHD (20 mol%), CH₃CN-H₂O (9 : 1 v/v) per mmol of substrate, R. T.

^bIsolated yields after column chromatography over silica gel; all carbonyl products (except 16a) are known compounds and were identified from their spectral data (FTIR, NMR and MS), m.p. and by comparison with authentic samples (Co-TLC, superimposable IR, mixed m.p.)³².

^cYield was assessed from 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative.

providing an opportunity for selective deprotection. Thus, treatment of a mixture comprising 1 mmol each of 1,3-dithiane of 3-methoxy-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (vanillin) and 4-nitrobenzaldehyde with 0.2 mL of 30% H₂O₂ and TBCHD (20 mol%) for 1 h gave vanillin in 96% yield accompanied with 4-nitrobenzaldehyde in a meagre yield of 15%. Significantly, 1,3-dithiolanes (entries 21-23) that are usually more resistant to oxidative cleavage than 1,3-dithianes²⁹ underwent smooth demasking as also a non-activated substrate such as cyclohexanone 1,3-dithiane

(entry 19). On the other hand, substantial sizes of both sulfur and two C-4 bromine atoms would cause steric impediment to nucleophilic attack of sulfur on bromine resulting in drop in deprotection rate of camphor 1,3-dithiolane (7 h) (entry 24). Facile efficient deprotection was also achieved with some dithianes of heterocyclic carbonyl compounds such as 2-acetylthiophene and furan-2-aldehyde (entries 9, 10) without overoxidation or other side reactions. The reagent system was compatible with a number of phenol-protecting allyl and TBDPS ethers, amino-protecting NHBn and NHBoc groups and aryl acetate adding to its synthetic utility. It is worth mentioning that nearly 80% of the 2,4,6-tribromophenol released from TBCHD was recovered during workup which could be easily converted to TBCHD following literature procedure³⁰.

Previously, the scope of TBCHD as dedithioacetalization reagent has been explored for a limited number of cases (11 examples) with DMSO in chloroform³¹ with reported yields that were comparable with those obtained by our method. However, use of a considerable amount of halogenated solvent (28 mL of chloroform/mmol of substrate) in the process development is a serious drawback of this method from environmental standpoint. The current method not only avoids CHCl_3 but also replaces DMSO by a safer, nonpolluting oxidizer in the form of 30% aqueous hydrogen peroxide. A tentative catalytic cycle involved in the deprotection process is depicted in Scheme 2. Notably, nucleophilic attack of water on the sulfenium ion intermediate results in its cleavage to carbonyl compound with concomitant release of Br^- and H^+ . The proton so released provides the acidic medium require for oxidation of Br^- to Br^+ equivalent by H_2O_2 which then enters the catalytic cycle.

In conclusion, we have developed a method of dethioacetalization that is operationally simple, reasonably fast and high yielding for a wide range of substrates. The green features combined with compatibility with a number of common functional and protecting groups will hopefully make it a method of choice for dethioacetalization.

Scheme 2

Experimental

1,3-Propanedithiol, 1,2-ethanedithiol and benzenedithiol were procured from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH, Germany. SDS was procured from SRL, India. Bruker DPX-400 (400 MHz), Perkin-Elmer FTIR L120-000A and Applied Biosystems MDS Sciex API 3200 were used for recording ^1H and ^{13}C NMR, IR spectra and mass spectra of the compounds respectively. Light petrol used refers to the fraction boiling at 60–80 °C.

Cleavage of 2-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-1,3-dithiane (1) using 30% hydrogen peroxide and TBCHD: To a stirred solution of **1** (290 mg, 1.2 mmol) in aqueous acetonitrile ($\text{CH}_3\text{CN}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 9 : 1 v/v, 2.4 mL) were added freshly prepared TBCHD (99 mg, 24 mol%) and 30% H_2O_2 (0.25 mL, 2.3 mmol) at room temperature and the mixture was thoroughly stirred for 15 min. The reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, acetonitrile was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was extracted with ethyl acetate (2 × 5 mL). The organic layer was washed with 5% NaOH solution (3 × 3 mL), followed by brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). Concentration of the organic extract and elution through a short pad of silica gel with EtOAc-light petrol (1 : 10) afforded 3,4-methylenedioxybenzaldehyde (piperonal), m.p. 36–38 °C (lit.^{32a} 37 °C) (176 mg, 98%). The combined alkaline washing was treated with 6 (N) HCl until acidic and extracted with EtOAc. It was dried and concentrated to yield 2,4,6-tribromophenol (60 mg, 80%).

Characterization data of new compounds :

2-(4-Acetoxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-1,3-dithiane (4, Table 2) : White solid, m.p. 122–124 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3057, 3021, 2977, 2940, 2895, 1766, 1599, 1506, 1452, 1410, 1279, 1179, 1033, 908, 767 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.09 (1H, d, J 1.6 Hz), 7.05–6.97 (2H, m), 5.15 (1H, s), 3.85 (3H, s), 3.09–3.02 (2H, m), 2.94–2.89 (2H, m), 2.30 (3H, s), 2.20–2.14 (1H, m), 1.98–1.88 (1H, m) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 168.9, 151.2, 139.6, 137.9, 122.8, 120.1, 111.9, 55.9, 51.2, 32.1, 25.0, 20.7 ppm; MS (ESI+) : m/z 285 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$).

2-Methyl-2-(thiophen-2-yl)-1,3-dithiane (9, Table 2) : White solid, m.p. 64–66 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3093, 3083, 3065, 2975, 2929, 2821, 2803, 1425, 1274, 1226, 1274, 1062, 825, 704 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.25–7.22 (2H, m), 6.95 (1H, dd, J 3.6, 5.2 Hz), 2.96–2.89 (2H, m), 2.77–2.72 (2H, m), 2.06–1.99 (1H, m), 1.95–1.87 (1H, m), 1.85 (3H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 152.1, 127.1, 126.8, 126.2, 50.3, 34.5, 28.5, 24.4 ppm; MS (ESI+) : m/z 217 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$).

2-(4-Tert-butyl-diphenylsilyloxyphenyl)-1,3-dithiane (16, Table 2) : White solid, m.p. 84–86 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3069, 3047, 3029, 2931, 2956, 2856, 1602, 1505, 1471, 1427, 1269, 1164, 1109, 929, 917, 823, 701 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.70–7.68 (4H, m), 7.44–7.39 (6H, m), 7.18 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 6.70 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 5.05 (1H, s), 3.05–2.98 (2H, m), 2.89–2.83 (2H, m), 2.15–2.11 (1H, m), 1.89–1.85 (1H, m), 1.08 (9H, s); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 155.6, 135.5, 132.7, 131.6, 129.9, 128.7, 127.8, 119.8, 50.8, 32.2, 26.5, 25.1, 19.5 ppm; MS (ESI+) : m/z 451 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$).

4-(Tert-butyl-diphenylsilyloxy)benzaldehyde (16a, Table 2) : White solid, m.p. 108–110 °C; FTIR (KBr) : ν 3066, 3015, 2998, 2951, 2929, 2857, 2798, 1697, 1597, 1510, 1427, 1276, 1162, 903, 840 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 9.80 (1H, s), 7.71–7.69 (4H, m), 7.64 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.47–7.43 (2H, m), 7.39–7.36 (4H, m), 6.85 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 1.11 (9H, s); MS (ESI+) : m/z 361 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$).

2-Methyl-2-(4-N-tert-butoxycarbonylphenyl)-1,3-dithiane (17, Table 2) : White solid, m.p. 94–96 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3331, 2976, 2931, 1727, 1704, 1591, 1519, 1233, 1159, 1072, 804, 753 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz,

CDCl_3) : δ 7.84 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 7.35 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 6.51 (1H, bs), 2.73–2.68 (4H, m), 1.96–1.88 (2H, m), 1.72 (3H, s), 1.52 (9H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 152.8, 138.3, 137.2, 128.6, 118.5, 80.6, 53.6, 32.8, 28.3, 28.1, 24.7 ppm; MS (ESI+) : m/z 326 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$).

2-Methyl-2-(4-N-benzylphenyl)-1,3-dithiane (18, Table 2) : White amorphous solid; IR (KBr) : ν 3422, 3082, 3059, 2957, 2915, 2891, 1604, 1512, 1492, 1450, 1394, 1239, 1178, 1070, 958, 806, 727 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.65 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.35–7.30 (5H, m), 6.70 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 4.65 (2H, s), 2.83–2.69 (4H, m), 1.98–1.92 (2H, m), 1.84 (3H, s) ppm; MS (ESI+) : m/z 316 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$).

2-[Bis(phenylthio)methyl]phenol (25, Table 2) : White solid, m.p. 98–100 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3400, 3072, 3058, 1596, 1582, 1480, 1456, 1328, 1267, 1225, 1086, 1024, 862, 746 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.38–7.36 (4H, m), 7.25–7.23 (6H, m), 7.16–7.11 (2H, m), 6.84–6.74 (2H, m), 6.32 (1H, s), 5.70 (1H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 153.8, 133.7, 132.6, 129.7, 129.6, 128.9, 128.1, 124.1, 120.7, 117.1, 56.5 ppm; MS (ESI+) : m/z 347 ($\text{M}^+ + \text{Na}$).

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